

The Evaluation of Symptoms, Treatment Approaches, and Prognosis of Liver Abscesses

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Abstract:

Background and Aim: Liver abscess remains a significant diagnostic and therapeutic hurdle for the medical community. This condition poses a significant risk to life and can lead to serious complications if not addressed promptly. Consequently, timely diagnosis and suitable management at the earliest stage are crucial. This study examined the incidence, aetiology, clinical signs and symptoms, and management of liver abscesses among patients in the general surgery wards of a Tertiary Care Teaching Institute in India.

Material and Methods: This prospective study involved 120 patients diagnosed with liver abscesses, all of whom were admitted to the general surgery wards of a Tertiary Care Teaching Institute in India over the course of one year. Initially, the documentation included a thorough history of routine examinations and blood tests. Subsequently, an ultrasound was conducted in specific instances, followed by additional treatment measures.

Results: The findings indicate that the highest number of cases, totalling 55, or 45.83%, were observed in the age group of 40 to 49 years. Every one of the 120 cases of liver abscess documented in this study reported experiencing abdominal pain. In the study, abdominal distension was observed in 57 cases, accounting for 47.15% of the total. Fever was reported in 65 cases, representing 54.16%, while dysentery was noted in 21 cases, which is 17.5% of the total. In the current study, every one of the 120 cases of liver abscess reported experiencing abdominal pain. Abdominal distension was observed in 57 cases, accounting for 47.15% of the total. Fever was noted in 65 cases, representing 54.16%, while dysentery was reported in 21 cases, or 17.5% of the total.

Conclusion: Liver abscesses predominantly occur in young males who have a history of alcohol use. Regrettably, this condition continues to lead to considerable illness and suffering.

Keywords: Abdominal Distension, Dysentery, fever, Liver abscesses.

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Introduction

Liver abscesses are defined as accumulations of pus within the liver tissue, resulting from infections that may be bacterial, parasitic, fungal, or a combination of these pathogens. This condition is widespread, impacting individuals globally. In developing nations, approximately two-thirds of cases are attributed to amoebic bacteria, whereas in industrialized countries, pyogenic bacteria account for about three-quarters of cases. [1]

The recognition and treatment of liver abscesses remain a significant issue within the healthcare landscape. This condition poses significant risks and can be life-threatening. Liver abscess remains a significant diagnostic and therapeutic hurdle for the medical community. The two predominant types of liver abscesses are amoebic liver abscesses (ALA) and pyogenic liver abscesses (PLA). [2]

Amoebiasis is a prevalent infection in developing nations, often attributed to inadequate sanitation facilities. Approximately 10% of the global population is impacted by this condition. Amoebic liver abscess represents the most prevalent extraintestinal manifestation of amoebiasis. Approximately 3-9% of individuals are impacted by this condition. Amoebic liver abscess is prevalent in India, marking it as an endemic region for this condition. It could manifest as an acute abdominal condition necessitating urgent surgical intervention.

Spontaneous intraperitoneal rupture, as well as extra and retroperitoneal rupture, along with intrathoracic rupture, are commonly observed complications associated with liver abscesses. A delay in diagnosis can result in the rupture of a

liver abscess, potentially elevating both morbidity and mortality rates. [3] Pyogenic liver abscess is a condition that occurs with notable frequency. This complication is considered relatively uncommon in cases of intra-abdominal or biliary tract infections. The infection typically exhibits a polymicrobial character, stemming from its ascent through the gastrointestinal tract. [4] Recent findings indicate that around 40% of cases are associated with complications related to biliary tract diseases.

A recent report indicates a shift in the aetiologies of PLA, moving away from intra-abdominal infections like trauma and acute appendicitis towards conditions affecting the biliary tract. Interestingly, as many as 55% of PLA cases are classified as cryptogenic, lacking identifiable risk factors. PLA is a complex infection caused by multiple microbial agents, arising from an upward progression of disease originating in the gastrointestinal tract. It is considered a rare medical condition. The incidence of PLA varies between 8 and 22 cases per 1,000,000 individuals. [5]

The presence of clinical symptoms in both amoebic liver disease and pyogenic liver abscess complicates the process of achieving an early diagnosis. [6] This study examined the incidence, aetiology, clinical signs and symptoms, and management of liver abscesses among patients in the general surgery wards of a Tertiary Care Teaching Institute in India.

Material and Methods

This prospective study involved 120 patients diagnosed with liver abscesses, all of whom were treated in the general surgery wards of a Tertiary Care Teaching Institute in India over the course of one year. The study excluded cases involving hydatid cysts, solid masses, and both primary and secondary liver malignancies.

In this study, all participants provided signed consent, and data were meticulously gathered using a standardized form. This form encompassed a range of information, including demographic details, clinical presentations of liver abscesses, associated risk factors, existing medical conditions, and results from laboratory tests such as microbiological cultures from blood and/or aspirates, stool examinations, and amoebic serology.

Additionally, it documented the type of imaging studies conducted, characteristics of the abscesses (including site, size, and number), as well as the types of interventions performed and the duration of hospital admissions.

The responsibility for selecting interventions was assigned to the consultants overseeing the patient's care. Daily examinations were conducted to assess the clinical improvement of the patients. The

criteria for successful treatment included improvements in pain, fever, anorexia, and hepatomegaly.

Statistical analysis

The collected data was organized and input into a spreadsheet application (Microsoft Excel 2019) before being exported to the data editor interface of SPSS version 19 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Quantitative variables were characterized using means and standard deviations or medians and interquartile ranges, depending on their distribution patterns. Qualitative variables were reported in terms of counts and percentages. The confidence level for all tests was established at 95%, while the level of significance was set at 5%.

Results

A comprehensive study was conducted involving 120 patients diagnosed with liver abscesses, representing a diverse range of age groups. The study involved patients aged between 30 and 65 years, comprising 116 men and 4 women diagnosed with both types of liver abscesses. The present analysis reveals that the highest incidence was observed in the 40-49 age group, accounting for 55 cases, or 45.83%.

This was followed by 25 cases (20.83%) in the 50-59 age range, 21 cases (17.5%) in the 30-39 age group, and 19 cases (15.83%) among individuals aged 60 and above. The prevalence of this disease is significantly higher in males, accounting for 96.6%, and compared to just 3.33% in females. In a study involving 120 cases, it was observed that 68 individuals had a history of alcohol consumption. Among these cases, amoebic abscesses were predominant, accounting for 64 instances, which represents 94.11% of the total. In contrast, pyogenic abscesses were noted in 4 cases, making up 5.88% of the findings. Table 1.

PLA and ALA exhibit the same clinical manifestations. In the current study, every one of the 120 cases of liver abscess reported experiencing abdominal pain. In the study, abdominal distension was observed in 57 cases, accounting for 47.15% of the total. Fever was noted in 65 cases, representing 54.16%, while dysentery was reported in 21 cases, which is 17.5% of the total.

The clinical presentation of a liver abscess typically involves symptoms such as fever, tenderness in the right upper quadrant, and elevated inflammatory markers. Every case presented with tenderness in the intercostal region and pain in the hypochondrial area. Hepatomegaly was observed in 45.83% of the cases. Jaundice was observed in 29 cases, accounting for 24.16%, while an epigastric mass was identified in 16 cases, representing 13.33% of the total.

In the current study, among the 99 cases examined, the predominant type of abscess identified was the right lobe abscess, accounting for 76 instances, or 63.33% of the total cases. In the study, there were 11 cases of left lobe abscesses, accounting for 9.16% of the total instances. Additionally, 7 cases of multiple abscesses were reported, representing 5.83%. Furthermore, there were 26 instances of ruptured abscesses, which comprised 21.66% of the

total. Table 2. Our research revealed that single aspiration was utilised in 34 cases, accounting for 28.33% of the total. Percutaneous catheter drainage was performed in 29 cases, representing 24.16%. Laparotomy and drainage were conducted in 26 cases, which is 21.66%. Multiple aspirations were carried out in 24 cases, making up 20%, while conservative management was applied in 5 cases, or 4.16%. Table 2.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of study patients

Variables	Number	Percentage (%)
Age		
30-39	21	17.5
40-49	55	45.83
50-59	25	20.83
60 and more than 60	19	15.83
Gender		
Male	116	96.6
Female	4	3.33

Table 2: Clinical manifestations of study patients

Variable	Number	Percentage (%)
Clinical symptoms		
Abdominal pain	120	100
Fever	65	54.16
Abdominal distension	57	47.15
Dysentery	21	17.5
Clinical signs		
Right hypochondrial tenderness	120	100
Intercostal tenderness	120	100
Hepatomegaly	55	45.83
Jaundice	29	24.16
Epigastric mass	16	13.33
Lobe wise distribution of liver abscess		
Right lobe	76	63.33
Ruptured abscess	26	21.66
Left lobe	11	9.16
Multiple abscesses	7	5.83
Treatment		
Single aspiration	34	28.33
Percutaneous catheter drainage	29	24.16
Laparotomy and drainage	26	21.66
Multiple aspirations	24	20
Conservative management	5	4.16

Discussion

Liver abscess (LA) is a prevalent condition in tropical regions, particularly in the Indian subcontinent. The most prevalent etiological agents for LA include *E. histolytica* (amoebic), bacterial (pyogenic) infections, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, and various fungi. Both ALA and PLA are prevalent conditions that exhibit similar signs and symptoms. However, the current diagnostic testing methods available are limited in their effectiveness. Even with the presence of numerous sensitisation facilities, a strong emphasis on personal hygiene

awareness, and a wide range of antimicrobials and medications, liver abscess remains one of the most common liver diseases. [7] This study aims to explore the epidemiology, clinical presentation, and management strategies associated with liver abscess cases. The findings of our study indicate that liver abscesses predominantly impact individuals in the 40-49 age bracket, representing 45.83% of cases. The findings align with those of Ahsan et al, who identified an increased risk of pyogenic abscess in this particular age group. [8]

ALA can manifest at any age; however, it is predominantly observed in adults aged 30 to 50 years. Liver abscesses occur more frequently in males compared to females. The reason behind this significant disparity remains unclear; however, it is probably linked to hormonal influences, alcohol intake, and the consumption of contaminated food and water.[9] Our findings align with earlier research indicating a higher prevalence of males. [10] The results align with previous studies indicating a higher prevalence among males. [11] Men who engage in high alcohol consumption face an elevated risk of developing an ALA. Alcohol negatively affects the function of Kupffer cells in the liver, hindering their capacity to eliminate amoeba. Invasive amoebiasis is associated with diets high in iron, often found in country whisky, as well as those rich in carbohydrates. [12]

In terms of causative factors, the gut and biliary microflora predominantly consist of gram-negative organisms, with *E. coli* emerging as the most frequently encountered pathogen. The current research findings indicate that ALA was present in 90.83% of the cases, while PLA was identified in 11 cases, accounting for 9.16%. The findings were consistent with prior experiences. [13]

Most patients reported experiencing abdominal pain accompanied by fever. This aligns with findings from another study, where abdominal pain and fever emerged as prevalent symptoms among participants. Abdominal tenderness in the right upper quadrant is frequently noted, with hepatomegaly occurring in half of the patients examined. [14] Our findings align with the previous research conducted by Abdullah et al. and Kebede et al. [8,15]

Our research indicates that the right lobe of the liver is the most frequently affected area, representing around 63% of cases. This finding aligns with the outcomes observed by other researchers. [13,15] Research indicates that the formation of liver abscesses is more prevalent in the right lobe compared to the left lobe of the liver. It appears that the right side of the lobe exhibits a greater volume of blood flow compared to the left side. [8,16] The observed phenomenon can be attributed to the fact that the right side of the lobe experiences a greater blood flow compared to the left side.

A total of 21.66% of the ruptured abscess cases necessitated a laparotomy and drainage procedure. A mere 4.16% of patients presenting with abscesses measuring less than 5 centimetres were treated conservatively. A study conducted by Zerem and his colleagues revealed that single or multiple aspirations achieved success in 67% of patients, while percutaneous catheter drainage proved effective for all patients involved. [17] Other

studies have reported comparable findings. [18,19] The limitation of this study lies in its design; it was conducted in a hospital setting rather than being population-based.

Conclusion

Liver abscesses were observed to be more prevalent among individuals aged 41 to 50. The prevalence of liver abscesses shows a striking gender disparity, with males significantly outnumbering females at a rate of 97.9%. In a significant finding, a history of alcohol consumption was noted in two-thirds of the cases involving liver abscesses. Instances of ALA were more prevalent, whereas pyogenic cases accounted for only 10%. *Escherichia coli*, the most prevalent organism, was responsible for the occurrence of PLA. In instances where aspiration proved unsuccessful, percutaneous catheter drainage was employed. Conversely, for ruptured abscesses, the preferred approach involved laparotomy and subsequent drainage.

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